

Vibration and Damping Analysis of Cross-ply Laminated Plates by the Finite Element Method Based on the Generalized Laminated Plate Theory

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Abstract

In order to investigate the effects of layer-wise in-plane displacements on vibration and damping characteristics of composite laminated plates, the finite element method based on the generalized laminated plate theory has been formulated. Specific damping capacity of each mode was obtained by modal strain energy method. The numerical results show that through-the-thickness variation of in-plane displacements is less important to the natural frequency, but has a great influence on the damping of composite plates, especially on the damping of thick composite plates since the damping is affected by local behavior while the natural frequency is affected by global behavior. Also, the cross-ply ratio of composite laminate affects the vibration and damping characteristics.

Keywords: Composite, Damping, Transverse shear, Vibration.

Introduction

The transverse shear deformation plays an important role in the anisotropic plates since most of the advanced composites have a low ratio of the transverse shear modulus to the modulus in the fiber direction. Although the shear deformation plate theory is adequate for predicting the global responses of medium-thick laminated plates, such as deflection, natural frequency and buckling load, it fails to give the accurate prediction of stress distribution and in-

plane displacements through thickness. The fact that the damping characteristics is affected by local behavior of plate deformation while the natural frequency is determined by global deformation, requires the refined theory for the damping analysis of the composite laminated plates.

The various approaches used for modelling multilayered composite plates were reviewed by Noor and Burton.¹ For free vibration problems, only the fundamental frequency and the associated mode shape were considered in several papers.^{2,4} However, the effect of the in-plane displacements on the damping characteristics of composite laminates has not been studied in their papers.

Research on the damping analysis of composite plates is not so extensive as that on the undamped free vibration analysis. Lin, Ni and Adams⁵ proposed a damped element model based on the modal strain energy (MSE) method to predict the specific damping capacity (SDC). Pervez and Zabar⁶ utilized the higher order shear deformation finite elements for the calculation of the SDC. Hwang and Gibson⁷ studied the coupling effect on the damping behavior of laminated composite beam by decomposing the dissipated energy according to stress components. However, the effects of the transverse shear deformation on the damping characteristics were not considered although three-dimensional, eight-node, thick shell element of SAP IV program was used. In spite of the valuable insight of the previous research, the effect of the in-plane displacement variation through thickness has not been investigated

intensively.

In this paper, the effects of the in-plane displacements on the vibration and damping characteristics are investigated for the cross-ply laminated plates in cylindrical bending vibration. The cylindrical bending problem makes the physical interpretation be clear without confronting the additional complexities of fully three-dimensional behavior. The objective of this work is to investigate the effect of the variation of the in-plane displacements through the thickness and the transverse shear deformation on the vibration and damping for the cross-ply laminated plates.

Analysis

Hamilton's principle of GLPT

Consider a cross-ply laminate composed of n layers in cylindrical bending as shown in Figure 1. Since the solution is independent of y and there is no displacement in the y direction, the displacement field should be expressed of the form

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, z, t) &= u_0(x, t) + U(x, z, t) \\ w(x, z, t) &= w_0(x, t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where u_0 and w_0 are the displacements in the middle plane and $U(x, 0, t) = 0$. In Eq. (1), the transverse normal strain is neglected, which is particularly true for the vibrational response.¹

Based on the generalized laminated plate theory (GLPT)⁸, U is approximated across the coordinate z as

$$U(x, z, t) = \sum_{j=1}^N U_j(x, t) \Phi^j(z) \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of degrees of freedom along the thickness and $\Phi^j(z)$ is the Lagrangian linear interpolation function.

Neglecting body forces and specified tractions, Hamilton's principle can be stated as

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T \int_0^l [N_x \frac{\partial \delta u_0}{\partial x} + Q_x \frac{\partial \delta w_0}{\partial x} + \sum_{j=1}^N (N_x^j \frac{\partial \delta U_j}{\partial x} + Q_x^j \delta U_j) \\ + I_0 (\ddot{u}_0 \delta u_0 + \ddot{w}_0 \delta w_0) + \sum_{j=1}^N I^j (\ddot{U}_j \delta u_0 + \ddot{u}_0 \delta U_j) \\ + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N \delta U_j I^{jk} \ddot{U}_k - q \delta w_0] dx dt = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the mass density and q is the distributed transverse load applied in the middle plane and

$$\begin{aligned} (N_x, Q_x, N_x^j, Q_x^j) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\sigma_x, \sigma_z, \sigma_x \Phi^j, \sigma_z \frac{d\Phi^j}{dx}) dz \\ (I_0, I^j, I^{jk}) &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \rho (1, \Phi^j, \Phi^j \Phi^k) dz \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

The constitutive relation for each orthotropic lamina at a specific fiber orientation is

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_z \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{Q}_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{Q}_{55} \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \gamma_z \end{Bmatrix}_k \quad (5)$$

where \bar{Q}_{pq} is the transformed reduced stiffness.⁹ The constitutive equations of the laminate are obtained by substituting Eq. (5) into Eq. (4).

$$N = A e + \sum_{j=1}^N B^j e_j \quad (6a)$$

$$N^j = B^j e + \sum_{k=1}^N D^{jk} e_k \quad (6b)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} N &= \begin{Bmatrix} N_x \\ Q_x \end{Bmatrix}, N^j = \begin{Bmatrix} N_x^j \\ Q_x^j \end{Bmatrix}, e = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_0}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v_0}{\partial x} \end{Bmatrix}, e_j = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\partial U_j}{\partial x} \\ U_j \end{Bmatrix} \\ A &= \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & 0 \\ 0 & A_{55} \end{bmatrix}, B^j = \begin{bmatrix} B_{11}^j & 0 \\ 0 & B_{55}^j \end{bmatrix}, D^{jk} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{11}^{jk} & 0 \\ 0 & D_{55}^{jk} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The components of the matrices in Eq. (7), are given by

$$\begin{aligned} (A_{11}, A_{55}) &= \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} (\bar{Q}_{11}, \bar{Q}_{55})_k dz \\ (B_{11}^j, B_{55}^j) &= \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} (\bar{Q}_{11} \Phi^j, \bar{Q}_{55} \frac{d\Phi^j}{dz})_k dz \\ (D_{11}^{jk}, D_{55}^{jk}) &= \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_k}^{z_{k+1}} (\bar{Q}_{11} \Phi^j \Phi^k, \bar{Q}_{55} \frac{d\Phi^j}{dz} \frac{d\Phi^k}{dz})_k dz \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where n is the number of layers. Substitution of Eq. (6) into Eq. (3) gives the compact form of the Hamilton's principle as follows:

$$\int_0^T \int_0^l [\delta e^T A e + \sum_{j=1}^N (\delta e^j T B^j e_j + \delta e_j^T B^j e)]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{\kappa=1}^N \delta \mathbf{e}_j^T \mathbf{D}^{j\kappa} \mathbf{e}_\kappa + \delta \mathbf{d}^T \mathbf{I} \mathbf{d} + \sum_{j=1}^N I' (\delta u_0 \ddot{U}_j + \delta U_j \ddot{u}_0) \\
& + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{\kappa=1}^N \delta U_j I'^{\kappa} \ddot{U}_\kappa] dx dt = \int_0^T \int_0^l q \delta w_0 dx dt \quad (9)
\end{aligned}$$

where

$$\mathbf{d} = \begin{Bmatrix} u_0 \\ w_0 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{I} = \begin{bmatrix} I_0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Finite element formulation

Over each finite element, the displacements (u_0, w_0, U_j) are expressed as a linear combination of shape functions $\hat{\psi}_i$ and the nodal values (u_0^i, w_0^i, U_j^i) as follows:

$$(u_0, w_0, U_j) = \sum_{i=1}^m (u_0^i, w_0^i, U_j^i) \hat{\psi}_i \quad (11)$$

where m is the number of nodes per element. Then, using Eq. (11), Hamilton's principle in Eq. (9) can be written in the form of the finite element formulation:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{\varepsilon=1}^{N_e} \int_0^T \int_{I_\varepsilon} [\delta \mathbf{u}_0^T \mathbf{H}_1^T \mathbf{A} \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{u}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^N (\delta \mathbf{u}_j^T \mathbf{H}_1^T \mathbf{B}' \mathbf{H}_2 \mathbf{u}_j \\
& + \delta \mathbf{u}_j^T \mathbf{H}_2^T \mathbf{B}' \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{u}_0) + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{\kappa=1}^N \delta \mathbf{u}_j^T \mathbf{H}_2^T \mathbf{D}^{j\kappa} \mathbf{H}_2 \mathbf{u}_j \\
& + \delta \mathbf{u}_0^T \mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{I} \mathbf{G} \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^N I' (\delta \mathbf{u}_0^T \mathbf{g}_j^T \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_j + \delta \mathbf{u}_j^T \mathbf{g}_2 \mathbf{g}_1^T \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_0) \\
& + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{\kappa=1}^N \delta \mathbf{u}_j^T \mathbf{g}_2 I'^{\kappa} \mathbf{g}_2^T \ddot{\mathbf{u}}_\kappa] dx dt = \sum_{\varepsilon=1}^{N_e} \int_0^T \int_{I_\varepsilon} q \delta \mathbf{u}_0^T \mathbf{g}_3 dx dt
\end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

where N_e is the number of elements and

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{u}_0^T &= \{u_0^1 \cdots u_0^m \quad w_0^1 \cdots w_0^m\}, \quad \mathbf{u}_j^T = \{U_j^1 \cdots U_j^m\} \\
\mathbf{g}_1^T &= \{\hat{\psi}_1 \cdots \hat{\psi}_m \quad 0 \cdots 0\}, \quad \mathbf{g}_2^T = \{\hat{\psi}_1 \cdots \hat{\psi}_m\} \\
\mathbf{g}_3^T &= \{0 \cdots 0 \quad \hat{\psi}_1 \cdots \hat{\psi}_m\}
\end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{H}_1 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_1}{\partial x} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_m}{\partial x} & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_1}{\partial x} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_m}{\partial x} \end{bmatrix} \\
\mathbf{H}_2 &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_1}{\partial x} & \cdots & \frac{\partial \hat{\psi}_m}{\partial x} \\ \hat{\psi}_1 & \cdots & \hat{\psi}_m \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} \hat{\psi}_1 & \cdots & \hat{\psi}_m & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & \hat{\psi}_1 & \cdots & \hat{\psi}_m \end{bmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

Since the virtual displacements are arbitrary, we obtain the following governing equation after assembly of the whole elements:

$$\mathbf{M} \ddot{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f} \quad (14)$$

For the free vibration analysis, the equation of motion takes the form of a standard eigenvalue problem:

$$(\mathbf{K} - \omega^2 \mathbf{M}) \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (15)$$

Specific damping capacity

The specific damping capacity is defined as:

$$\Psi = \frac{\Delta E}{E} \quad (16)$$

where ΔE is the energy dissipated per cycle and E is the maximum strain energy. The dissipated energy of the composite laminate in cylindrical bending vibration is composed of two components:

$$\Delta E = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} (\psi_x \sigma_x \varepsilon_x + \psi_{xx} \sigma_{xx} \gamma_{xx}) dz dx \quad (17)$$

After integrating Eq. (17) through thickness, the dissipated energy can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Delta E &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l [\mathbf{e}^T \hat{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{e} + \sum_{j=1}^N (\mathbf{e}^T \hat{\mathbf{B}}^j \mathbf{e}_j + \mathbf{e}_j^T \hat{\mathbf{B}}^j \mathbf{e}) \\
& + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{\kappa=1}^N \mathbf{e}_j^T \hat{\mathbf{D}}^{j\kappa} \mathbf{e}_\kappa] dx
\end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
(\hat{\mathbf{A}}_{11}, \hat{\mathbf{A}}_{55}) &= \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{I_k} (\hat{\mathcal{Q}}_{11}, \hat{\mathcal{Q}}_{55})_k dz \\
(\hat{\mathbf{B}}'_{11}, \hat{\mathbf{B}}'_{55}) &= \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{I_k} (\hat{\mathcal{Q}}_{11} \Phi', \hat{\mathcal{Q}}_{55} \frac{d\Phi'}{dz})_k dz \\
(\hat{\mathbf{D}}^{j\kappa}, \hat{\mathbf{D}}^{j\kappa}) &= \sum_{k=1}^N \int_{I_k} (\hat{\mathcal{Q}}_{11} \Phi^j \Phi^\kappa, \hat{\mathcal{Q}}_{55} \frac{d\Phi^j}{dz} \frac{d\Phi^\kappa}{dz})_k dz
\end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

and $\hat{\mathcal{Q}}$ in Eq. (19), are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\hat{\mathcal{Q}}_{11} &= \psi_1 Q_{11} \cos^4 \theta + (\psi_1 Q_{12} + \psi_2 Q_{21} \\
& + 4 \psi_{12} Q_{66}) \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta + \psi_2 Q_{22} \sin^4 \theta \\
\hat{\mathcal{Q}}_{55} &= \psi_{13} Q_{55} \cos^2 \theta + \psi_{23} Q_{44} \sin^2 \theta
\end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where θ is the fiber orientation and ψ_i are the specific damping capacities related with their stress components. Their definitions are described well in Ref. 5.

With the similar way to that used in the finite

element method, the total dissipated energy can be discretized as followings:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E &= \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{u}^T \mathbf{K}_d \mathbf{u} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{N_1} \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_i} [\mathbf{u}_0^T \mathbf{H}_1^T \hat{\mathbf{A}} \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{u}_0 + \sum_{j=1}^N (\mathbf{u}_j^T \mathbf{H}_1^T \hat{\mathbf{B}}^j \mathbf{H}_2 \mathbf{u}_j \\ &\quad + \mathbf{u}_j^T \mathbf{H}_2^T \hat{\mathbf{B}}^j \mathbf{H}_1 \mathbf{u}_0) + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{u}_j^T \mathbf{H}_2^T \hat{\mathbf{D}}^{jk} \mathbf{H}_2 \mathbf{u}_k] dx \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where \mathbf{K}_d is the damped stiffness matrix.

The specific damping capacity for each mode are computed from Eq. (16) as

$$\Psi_i = \frac{\phi_i^T \mathbf{K}_d \phi_i}{\phi_i^T \mathbf{K} \phi_i} \quad (22)$$

where ϕ_i are the i -th modal vector obtained from the eigenanalysis of Eq. (15).

Results and Discussions

Numerical computations are carried out for the cylindrical bending vibration analysis of simply supported symmetric cross-ply plates. The effects of cross-ply ratio on fundamental frequencies and SDC are investigated for thick and thin laminates.

For the purpose of comparison with the reported results, the following material properties of a unidirectional fiber reinforced composite are used:

$$E_1/E_2=25, G_{12}/E_2=G_{13}/E_2=0.5, G_{23}/E_2=0.2, \nu_{12}=0.25 \\ \psi_1=0.0045, \psi_2=0.0422, \psi_{12}=\psi_{13}=\psi_{23}=0.0705$$

The distributed loading for static analysis is assumed to be a sinusoidal loading:

$$q = q_0 \sin\left(\frac{\pi x}{l}\right) \quad (23)$$

The following normalized variables are used in presenting the results:

$$\bar{u} = \frac{u E_2 h^2}{q_0 l^3} \times 100, \quad \bar{\omega} = \omega l^2 \sqrt{\frac{\rho E_2}{h^2}}, \quad \bar{z} = \frac{z}{h} \quad (24)$$

Figure 2 shows the in-plane displacements of simply supported $[0/90/0]_T$ plate in cylindrical bending under sinusoidal loading, where l/h is 4.

Table 1. Fundamental frequencies, $\bar{\omega}$ of $[0/90]_S$ plates in cylindrical bending vibration.

l/h	Present		Whitney ¹¹
	$N = 4$	$N = 2$	(FSDT)
5	6.5324	7.6323	7.1549
10	9.8924	10.8655	10.4898
20	12.1854	12.6152	12.4379
50	13.1974	13.2820	13.2148
100	13.3644	13.3863	13.3383

CLPT solution = 13.3802

The GLPT(present) solution is in an excellent agreement with 3D-elasticity¹⁰, while the CLPT (classical laminated plate theory) gives considerable error.

Table 1 shows the effects of thickness on the normalized fundamental frequencies of $[0/90]_S$ plate in cylindrical bending vibration. The results for $N = n$ are obtained by dividing the laminate through thickness into n . Those for $N = 2$, which are close to solutions of first-order shear deformation theory (FSDT) in case of symmetric laminates, are obtained by dividing the laminate into two. The results for $N = n$ are more accurate than those for $N = 2$. For thin plates, the results of $N = 2$ and FSDT are in a good agreement with those of $N = 4$. However, there are some differences among them as l/h decreases. The results for $N = 4$ are much more accurate than those for FSDT.

The variation of the in-plane displacements $\bar{u}(0, \bar{z})$ for various cross-ply ratio m are shown in Figure 3 when $[0/90]_S$ plates are subjected to the sinusoidal loading. The length-to-thickness ratio, l/h is 5 in this case. The thickness of the cross-ply laminates are of the same for the various cross-ply ratios and the cross-ply ratio is defined as follows:

$$m = \frac{\text{total thickness of } 0^\circ \text{ layer}}{\text{total thickness of } 90^\circ \text{ layer}} \quad (25)$$

The results in Figure 3 imply that the variation of the in-plane displacements through thickness can have a great influence on the local behavior such as the damping characteristics of composite laminates.

Figure 4 shows the fundamental frequencies

and the specific damping capacities (SDC) for a simply-supported thin plate with $l/h = 50$. As the cross-ply ratio increases, the natural frequency increases. There is a little difference between the fundamental frequencies for $N = 4$ and $N = 2$ in this thin plate. However, the SDC's for $N = 2$ are estimated smaller than those for $N = 4$. This is mainly due to the underestimation of the transverse shear deformation for $N = 2$ as shown in Figure 5. The transverse shear strain energies for $N = 2$ are underestimated by neglecting the variation of the in-plane displacements through the thickness. The SDC decreases as the cross-ply ratio increases. The strain energies for the plate has two components: the bending strain energy, W_{xx} and the transverse shear strain energy, W_{xz} . Figure 5 shows the transverse shear strain energy W_{xz} for the previous thin plate. The bending strain energy, W_{xx} is more than 95% of the total strain energy. The effect of the transverse shear deformation on damping characteristics is small for this thin plate. Therefore, the damping characteristics of the laminate in bending are severely dependent on the amount of 90° layer. Hence, as m , the ratio of the thickness of 0° layer to 90° layer increases, the SDC decreases.

The results for a thick $[0/90]_s$ plate with $l/h = 5$ are shown in Figure 6. These results for the thick plate are different from those for the thin plate with $l/h = 50$. In this thick plate, there is considerable error in the frequencies and the SDC's for $N = 2$. The SDC is the highest near $m = 4/6$. Figure 7 illustrates how the results for $l/h = 5$ are different from those for $l/h = 50$. This figure shows the transverse shear strain energy for the thick plates with $l/h = 5$. There is a large amount of transverse shear deformation which is the largest at $m = 4/6$. This makes the SDC be maximum at $m = 4/6$. Therefore, it is concluded from this fact that the SDC for a thick laminate is severely dependent on the amount of the transverse shear and the accurate estimation of the SDC requires the multilayered theory which can describe well the in-plane displacement variation through thickness.

Conclusions

In order to investigate the effects of the layer-wise in-plane displacements on the vibration

and damping characteristics of composite laminated plates, the finite element method based on the generalized laminated plate theory has been formulated. The specific damping capacity of each mode was obtained by the modal strain energy method. The numerical results show that through-the-thickness variation of in-plane displacements has not much influence on the natural frequency, but has a great influence on the damping of composite plates, especially on the damping of thick composite plates since the damping is affected by local behavior while the natural frequency is affected by global behavior. Also, the cross-ply ratio of composite laminate affects the vibration and damping characteristics because it determines the deformation pattern such as bending and transverse shear deformation. For the thick plate, there exists certain cross-ply ratio, nearly 1.0, which makes the highest damping. For the thin plate, the smaller the cross-ply ratio becomes, the higher the specific damping capacity becomes.

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Figure 1. Coordinate system of laminated plate in cylindrical bending.

Figure 2. In-plane displacements of simply supported $[0/90/0]_T$ plate in cylindrical bending under sinusoidal loading: $l/h = 4$.

Figure 3. Variation of in-plane displacements for simply supported $[0/90]_s$ plates with cross-ply ratio: $l/h = 5$.

Figure 4a. Effects of cross-ply ratio on fundamental frequencies for $[0/90]_s$ plates: $l/h = 50$.

Figure 5. Percentage of transverse shear strain energy W_{xz} of thin $[0/90]_s$ plates: $l/h = 50$.

Figure 4b. Effects of cross-ply ratio on SDC's for $[0/90]_s$ plates: $l/h = 50$.

Figure 6a. Effects of cross-ply ratio on fundamental frequencies for $[0/90]_s$ plates: $l/h = 5$.

Figure 6b. Effects of cross-ply ratio on SDC's for $[0/90]_s$ plates: $l/h = 5$.

Figure 7. Percentage of transverse shear strain energy W_{xz} of thick $[0/90]_s$ plates: $l/h = 5$.